

FAILURE PROCESS IN CARBON FIBER REINFORCED ALUMINUM COMPOSITES

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Summary

The failure process in carbon fiber reinforced aluminum composites (C/Al) has been investigated by measuring its tensile strength, and acoustic emission behavior during loading combined with the analysis of the fracture morphology. The result shows that the failure process is very complicated and the tensile strength of C/Al composites is related to the fracture morphology and the acoustic emission feature.

Introduction

C/Al composites have high potential for use in the fields of aerospace and aeronautics due to their excellent combination of properties. In order to provide a factor of safety and optimize their use, the investigation of the composite failure process is very important.

Since C/Al composites are inhomogeneous materials, the fracture mechanism is complicated and the process of fracture is not straightforward. I. M. Kopyov (1) attempted to predict the strength properties and failure appearance by using computer simulation of failure process in C/Al composites, but was unsuccessful in correlating this with experimentally observed failure process. Xian (2) has employed acoustic emission (AE) techniques to monitor the damage process of the fibrous composites.

In this work, we measure the tensile strength of some typical C/Al specimens while simultaneously monitoring the acoustic emission. The relationship between the tensile strength, AE feature and fracture morphology of different specimens can be used to understand the failure process of C/Al composites.

Experimental Procedures

Preparation of Specimens

Composites were fabricated using type II PAN-based carbon fibers from Shanghai Carbon Factory and type LD₂ Al foils*. The C/Al precursor wires are fabricated by liquid metal impregnation. The C/Al unidirectional composite plate is prepared by diffusion bonding in air. Fiber volume fraction is 26-28%. Specimens cut from the plate are 100 mm in length, 6 mm in width and 2-3 mm in thickness.

Testing Procedure

Tension tests were performed on a Japan-made universal testing machine model DSC-25T at a loading speed of 0.5 mm per minute. During loading, the load and strain are recorded in the AE instrumentation as pattern parameters 1 and 2. The AE features are measured using an AET-5000 made in the USA. A model MAC-300 microsensor (5 mm in diameter) with frequency limited to 300 KHZ is located on the specimens for receiving the AE signals. Fracture surface morphologies are characterized using a China-made scanning electron microscope model DSM-1.

Results and Discussion

The AE Feature as a Function of Failure Mode

The AE features of the metal matrix only, and the longitudinal and transverse tensile orientations of C/Al composites are shown in Table I. Fiber orientations and strengths of the specimens tested are listed in Table II. From

*Typical composition is as follows:

Cu	0.25	Mg	0.46	Fe	0.17	Si	1.09	Mn	0.25
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Table I: AE Feature and Tensile Strength of Typical Specimens

Specimen No		1	2	3	4	5	6
Total Gains dB		93	93	90	87	87	87
Total Events		3078	8780	11114	12645	10664	12129
Energy	Cumulated dB	1.12×10^5	3.8×10^5	8.0×10^5	7.09×10^5	5.82×10^5	8.36×10^5
	dB per Event	33.5	43.5	72	56.2	54.6	68.9
Ringdown Counts	Cumulated dB	3.46×10^5	1.08×10^5	0.9×10^5	2.73×10^5	2.58×10^5	6.9×10^5
	Mean Count per Event	118	12.4	8.1	21.6	24.2	50.8
Percentage of Total Cumulated Events and Energy in Different Energy Ranges	0-30 dB	Event	37.8	7.9	0	0	0
		Energy	33.5	11.5	0	0	0
	30-60 dB	Event	49.2	60.3	24.8	55.3	67.7
		Energy	60.2	98.4	18.3	44.3	55.6
	60-120 dB	Event	12.0	20.0	76.8	47	45.4
		Energy	24.3	28.9	80.8	63.2	63.8
	≥ 120 dB	Event	0	0	0.05	0.4	0.5
		Energy	0	0	0.09	0.7	1.4

Table I we note that the fracture energy of the matrix is the lowest, the energy of fiber-matrix interface debonding is mainly intermediate and the energy of fiber fracture is rather high, so we can roughly distinguish the type of fracture by the AE measurement.

The Relationship Between AE Feature, Fracture Morphology and Tensile Strength of C/Al Specimens

Table II illustrates tensile strength and fracture morphology features of typical specimens. The curves of AE events versus tensile strain ϵ and stress σ as well as the typical pictures of fracture morphology are shown in Figs. 1 and 2 respectively. It is evident that the tensile strength of C/Al composites may be

Table II. Tensile Strength and Fracture Morphology Feature

Specimen No.	Fiber Orientation	Tensile Strength Kg/mm ²	Fracture Morphology Feature
1	No fiber	13.5	necking failure of foil with some separation
2	90°	5.2	fiber-matrix debonding with some transverse fiber failure
3	0°	43.65	splinter like fracture surface exhibiting pulled out fibers of long length and plastically deformed matrix
4	0°	30	irregular fracture surface with fiber pullout length less than in 3
5	0°	22.4	smooth regions of brittle failure and bundle fracture with large debonding length
6	0°	22	brush-like fracture surface

Fig. 1. Total Events versus Strain and Stress

Specimen No. 1

X20

Specimen No. 2

X1000

Specimen No. 3

X500

Specimen No. 4

X500

Specimen No. 5

X100

Specimen No. 6

X20

Fig. 2. Typical Tensile Fracture Morphology

related to the acoustic emission feature and fracture morphology. High tensile strength generally correlates with a delay in high energy events during loading. For specimen No. 3, events with high energy and large ringdown counts occurred at the onset of fracture as shown in Fig. 3. The fracture morphology consists of pulled out fibers with long length and plastically deformed matrix (shown in Fig. 1). The fracture process consists of fiber failure followed by fiber pullout and matrix failure last. For this type of failure, the composite realizes the full potential of the fiber and matrix and the tensile strength is the highest. On the other hand, in the specimen No. 6 most of the fibers have not bonded well with the matrix. Soon after loading, the AE events appear and increase sharply with loading. The events are primarily high energy characteristic of fiber failure. The fracture morphology is brush like and consists of pulled out fibers with excessive debonding length. In this type of failure, the matrix is debonded from the fibers and is unable to effectively transfer the loading force. During loading the fibers are broken continuously up to the specimen fracture. The tensile strength of such a specimen is the lowest.

Fig. 3. Events with Different Energy versus Load

Obviously the tensile strength is rather low. For specimens of intermediate strength, ringdown counts of high energy indicative of fiber breakage are observed early on in the loading process but in combination with other energies as shown in Figs. 4 and 5. As seen in specimen No. 4, shorter fiber pullout lengths are associated with such a failure. In specimen No. 5, a greater number of events appear earlier. In this case, the fracture morphology exhibits both brittle regions and bundle fractures with large debonding length and separated fibers.

Energy and Peak Amplitude Distribution

The curves of energy distribution and peak amplitude distribution for all specimens are similar as shown in Fig. 6. It seems that the curve of energy distribution has two peaks, and the curve of peak amplitude distribution is in

Fig. 4. Mean Events Duration and Mean Ringdown Counts versus Time in Specimen No. 4

Fig. 5. AE Feature versus Time in Specimen No. 4

accordance with the normal distribution. The events with low energy are mainly produced by initial cracking, interface debonding and fibers pulling out. The events with high energy are mainly produced by fiber breakage.

Fig. 6. AE Events versus Energy and Peak Amplitude

Conclusions

The failure process in C/Al composites is very complicated. It includes the processes of initial cracking, crack extension, fiber-matrix interface debonding, fiber pullout and the fracture of fibers and matrix. Specific failure processes can be related to the energy level of acoustic emission. It has been shown that the ringdown count patterns for energy levels indicative of specific failure processes is a strong function of specimen fabrication.

The tensile strength and fracture mode of C/Al composites can be related to the AE feature. If the total number of events increases gradually, and events with high energy as well as large ringdown occur just prior to failure, then higher strength should be observed.

References

1. I. M. Kopyov, A. S. Ovchinsky and N. K. Bilsagayev, "Computer Simulation of Various Fracture Mechanisms in Fibrous Composite", paper presented at Fracture of Composite Materials, Proceedings of the Second USA-USSR Symposium, held at Lehigh University, Bethlehem, Pennsylvania, USA, Mar. 9-12, 1981.
2. Xian Xingjuan, Jiang Conxing, "Failure Behavior and Acoustic Emission Analysis of Multi-ply Carbon/Epoxy Composite Materials", ASTRONAUTICA SINICA, 5 (2) 1984 pp 241-247.